

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

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A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“ECHOES OF THE ECHO MARKET: UNCOVERING GAPS AND THE PATH FORWARD”

People are interested in following trends or what is new in the marketing places, that is why many businesses today would like to focus on what is trending in the market whether that is a product or service. Because of this, many businesses today focus on what is trending and the result is that many products and services look the same since these products and services are very popular in the market. But this situation may lead to too much competition because of so many similar products and services, it is very hard for the seller to meet the unique needs of a customer that may cause the gap in the echo market.

An echo market is a situation where businesses create the same trending products and services – an idea that is echoed across the market environment. Consumers also influence the market by choosing familiar and trending products. For example, milk tea shops are everywhere. Latest gadgets and fashion styles are also easily copied by many brands that may lead to market saturation because almost products in the market are the same.

In the echo market, consumers are exposed to the same ideas that may reduce the diversity of businesses in exploring new perspectives, they usually focus on copying instead of creating new ideas for the new product to offer to the consumers.

On the part of a small business that has a unique idea normally overlooked because popular brands and influencers dominate the attention of the consumers. So, small businesses with creative products usually get ignored because their ideas are not popular and usually consumers follow and buy what is trending in the market. Consumers' decisions regarding buying are based on the popularity of the product and not the quality and need of the consumers.

The gaps in the echo market affect the decision-making, innovation, and fairness of both the businesses and the consumers. Businesses compete by copying the products or services of the other instead of creating and innovating unique products and services. Target consumers or end users relying and depending on what is trend instead of what their real needs are. Diversity in this aspect is less; few unique ideas and perspectives are not shared that slows down economic progress.

In the echo market, gaps should be addressed by promoting diverse ideas and perspectives. Businesses should break the cycle of imitating but instead encourage creativity. Provide the small entrepreneurs with the

opportunity to start up and allow fresh ideas into the market. Reducing popular brands and start buying from local entrepreneurs and by promoting them through social media.

Consumers should think carefully before buying and availing trending products and services. Help businesses to avoid copying and imitating products and services. Encourage consumers to buy based on what they need, ensure quality and not for popularity.

Businesses should play fair competition and be responsible in marketing. Creates equal opportunities in the market. Better policies and regulations can help create a fair market environment. Government and organizations can strengthen the implementation of rules that support small entrepreneurs, ensure honest advertising, and promote innovation. These may prevent repetitive trends and provide equal opportunities to all market players. These solutions can help in building a more creative, fair, and sustainable market.

In conclusion, echo market highlights how repeated ideas and trends can shape the way consumers think, choose, and act. These gaps affect not only consumers and businesses but also the community by reducing diversity of thought.

Moving forward is essential for consumers and businesses to work together and overcome these gaps. Promoting many diverse ideas, supporting small entrepreneurs, and implementing equal policies leading to a more innovative and balanced market environment can be achieved. Ultimately, breaking away from the echo market allows new ideas to build a better opportunity for everyone.

